

TOURISM FACILITIES OF KASHKADARYA REGION AND THEIR USE IN GEOGRAPHY EDUCATION

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Abstract: *Through this article, we are going to explore important peculiarities of tourism facilities in Kashkadarya region and their use in geography education. Additionally, facts about the specific features of region that attract tourists all over the world were given.*

Key Words: *non-tourism, tourist-historic city, [Ecotourism](#), [Pamir-Alay](#) mountains, abundance, architectural monuments, cultural heritage, southwestern plains.*

Geography is the ideal discipline for studying the global tourism industry; as the key journal [Tourism Geographies](#) explains, there are many fundamentally geographical aspects to tourism which “occurs in places, is sold and begins in a place of origin and is consumed in destination places, transforms the environment of visited places in ways that are distinct from non-tourism processes, involves the movement of people, goods, services, ideas, and money over space, and presents a distinct way that people view, understand and relate to the world.” Given the inherently spatial aspects of tourism, geographers have contributed significantly to academic tourism studies. They have developed some of the most important conceptual models for explaining tourism development, including resort morphology, the tourist-historic city, and the tourist area life cycle. Additionally geographers have made the most sustained contributions to the study of the environmental dimensions of tourism and have been major contributors to the concepts of sustainable tourism and [Ecotourism](#). Even though it has been at the core of tourism studies and also strengthened geography department enrollments, tourism geography ironically has been somewhat peripheral in academic geography. This status may be due in part to the inertia of academic institutions and staff in not seeing tourism as a serious subject for study, as well as the difficulty in measuring the tourism industry as compared to primary and secondary industries.

Kashkadarya Region is one of the [regions of Uzbekistan](#), located in the south-eastern part of the country in the basin of the river [Kashqadaryo](#) and on the western slopes of the [Pamir-Alay](#) mountains. It borders with [Tajikistan](#), [Turkmenistan](#), [Samarqand Region](#), [Bukhara Region](#) and [Surxondaryo Region](#). It covers an area of 28,570 km². The population is estimated 3,408,345 (2022), with 57% living in rural areas. The regional capital is [Qarshi](#) (278,300 inhabitants). The Kashqadaryo Region consists of 13 [districts](#) (listed below) and two district-level cities: [Qarshi](#) and [Shahrisabz](#). There are 12 cities ([Qarshi](#), [Shahrisabz](#), [G'uzor](#), [Qamashi](#), [Beshkent](#), [Koson](#), [Kitob](#), [Muborak](#), [Yangi Nishon](#), [Tallimarjon](#), [Chiroqchi](#), [Yakkabog'](#)) and 117 [urban-type settlements](#) in the Qashqadaryo Region. The climate is a typically arid [continental climate](#) and partly [semi-tropical](#). The city of [Shahrisabz](#), the birthplace of Amir [Timur](#), is the main tourist attraction in the region.

Kashkadarya region is one of the most environmentally friendly, located in the basin of the Kashkadarya river. The toponym Kashkadarya has several meanings: "river lost in the sand" and "transparent, clean river". Due to the continental climate (sometimes even subtropical) on the slope of the Pamir-Alai mountains, the air in the region is the purest, and the natural landscape fascinates with its flora and fauna. There are several well-known nature reserves in the region - Kitab, Gissar and Kizil-say nature reserve. It is here in the foothills that the colorful jewels of nature are grown - pomegranates, quinces, peaches, pears, cherries, lemons. Huge abundance of vegetables, several types of nuts: pistachios, peanuts, walnuts. Spacious pastures allow you to raise livestock. And all this under the warm sun, among wide fields and ancient mounds.

In addition to the excellent ecology and beautiful nature, the region is rich in ancient cities and architectural monuments. The birthplace of the outstanding commander Amir Timur - the city of Shakhrisabz in Kashkadarya region is listed as a UNESCO World Cultural heritage. The formation of anthropogenic landscapes and population distribution in the Kashkadaryaregion are inextricably linked. According to the conducted researches, it can be seen that the most densely populated anthropogenic landscapes are located in Shahrisabz, Yakkabog, Kitab districts, located in the middle high mountains and foothills. If the regions of the country are divided into three groups (intensively used, extensively used and unused) according to the potential of existing tourism and recreation resources, intensively used make a small share, extensively used and almost unused make a large share. Consequently, while the regions have different tourist

and recreational resources, they are also involved in tourism and recreation activities to varying degrees. Today, the leading regional vector of tourism in our country is the route Tashkent-Samarkand-Bukhara-Khiva, historically formed under the influence of the Great Silk Road. Currently, the leading regional vector of formed touristic activities of our republic is the route of Tashkent-Samarkand-Bukhara-Khiva, which was historically formed under the influence of the Great Silk Road. Today the Republic of Uzbekistan has a great tourism and recreational potential. There are more than 7,400 cultural heritage sites in the country, 209 of them are located in four museum cities – Khiva, Bukhara, Samarkand and Shakhrisabz, and they are included in the UNESCO World Heritage List. It should be noted that in recent years, the influx of tourists to Uzbekistan has also increased. At the same time, 2.69 million foreign tourists visited Uzbekistan in 2017, increased to 5.3 million in 2018. The number of tourism organizations increased from 398 in 2015 to 950 by the end of 2018. During this time the number of hotel farms increased from 661 to 900 units. In 2010-2017, export volume of tourism services in Uzbekistan doubled, reached to 546.9 million US dollars in 2017 and 1.041 million in 2018 US dollars (The concept of tourism, 2019).

If the Karshi zone (the city of Karshi is the administrative, economic, scientific and cultural center of the region) is located in the southwestern plains – desert part of the region, the Kitab-Shakhrisabz zone covers the north-eastern and eastern foothills, mountain areas. Rural areas vary according to their territorial and demographic potential, economic specialization and production capacity, level of development, and as well as the potential of tourist recreational resources. Among them the Kitab-Shakhrisabz group of districts is characterized by tourist and recreational potential. Consequently, the potential of rural areas in terms of monuments of material and cultural heritage (archeological, architectural, monumental art monuments, sights) is closely connected, first of all, by their location, nature, dense or sparse population, especially the rich historical past and as well as the ancient land development and inhabiting of population. For example, in Kitab – Shakhrisabz group districts with favorable natural and geographical conditions and densely populated areas, there are many monuments of material and cultural heritage, but on the contrary, in newly developed rural areas of the region, (Mubarak, Nishon, Mirishkor) are characterized by small numbers and types. As of January 2019, in Kashkadarya region total 1311 (17.7% of the Republic of Uzbekistan) material and cultural historical monuments are registered. Of these, 1,041 are account for archeological monuments, 200 – for

architecture, 43 – for monuments of monumental art, 27 are for sights. They are located differently by the cities and rural areas of the region. As can be seen from the Table 1, indeed, the rural areas with the high potential of cultural historical material heritage of the region are Yakkabog (237), Shakhrisabz (159) and Kitab (158). They have embodied 42.2% of the region's potential in themselves. The famous scientist A.Kh. Soliev also highly appreciates the fact that “Shakhrisabz, Kitab, Yakkabog districts have many places of worship and pilgrimages”,

and “the ancient Shakhrisabz as the tourist destination is the birthplace of the great Amir Temur” (Soliev and Usmonov 2005). On the contrary, the districts with low potential are Nishon (7), Mubarek (8) and Mirishkor (18), that they are characterized by the fact that they are geographically located in the Karshi zone.

The largest number of tourist sites of material heritage of the region is archeological monuments. Most of them organize hills belonging to different periods, as well as castles, monuments, old house remnants, and others. As noted above, Yakkabog, Shakhrisabz and Kitab districts are the leaders by the number of such tourist resources, while the districts of Nishon, Mubarek and Mirishkor, on the contrary, are the lower levels. The number of existing architectural monuments in the region is 200; they include mosques, madrasas, old fortress walls, mausoleums, cisterns, bridges. In this regard, Yakkabog district (38), Shakhrisabz city (24), Kitab (16) and Chirakchi (16) are leading districts, on the contrary, the potential of Nishon (1) and Mubarek (3) districts in the Karshi steppe zone is weak. And all the other rural areas are intermediate position categories by the importance of the objects of tourist recreation.

To sum up, the peculiarity of the region in this regard is that most of them are connected with belonging to the republic. In particular, 985 or 75.1% out of the total (1311) material and cultural tourism recreation sites belong to the republican category and 24.8% are local category. This figure is 81.6% and 18.2% in archeological resources, 42.0% and 58.0% in architectural monuments. At the same time, all monuments of monumental art belong to the republican category, and on the contrary 70.3% of the sights are local category. It should be noted separately that the regional center – Karshi city (59 places) and Karshi district (1287) as well, takes a special place with cultural tourism potential. It is advisable to divide cities and rural areas of Kashkadarya region into three groups according to their material and cultural recreational potential.

REFERENCES:

1. S. I. Abdullaev, Rational use of land resources in relation to population growth, (Proceedings of the Republican scientific-methodical seminar on "Methods of teaching engineering and scientific research in the field of engineering and ecology"), 58-60 (2002)
2. A.A. Abulkasimov, Classification issues of anthropogenic landscapes of Central Asia, 26-30 (1966)
3. L.N. Babushkin, N.A. Kogay, Fundamentals of the methodology for assessing natural conditions for agriculture 64-73 (1975)
4. V.A. Baranov, A.V. Ivanov, Agroforestry landscapes of the southeast of European Russia: structure, evolution, optimization, 274 (Science Book, Saratov, 2006)